

CLINICAL AND IMAGING CHARACTERISTICS OF BONE TUMORS AND THEIR DIAGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract. This study aimed to evaluate the clinical and radiological characteristics of bone tumors. A retrospective study conducted from 2022 to 2025 included 41 patients aged 5-60 years, with all diagnoses confirmed histopathologically. According to the results, malignant tumors predominated (70.7%), with osteosarcoma and Ewing sarcoma being the most common. A comprehensive clinical and radiological assessment plays an important role in the early detection and differential diagnosis of bone tumors.

Keywords: bone tumors, MRI, radiography, osteosarcoma, Ewing sarcoma.

Introduction

Bone tumors occurring in children and adolescents occupy a distinct place among oncological diseases. They are characterized by relatively low incidence, clinical heterogeneity, and a tendency toward aggressive biological behavior [1,2]. In particular, osteosarcoma and Ewing sarcoma are distinguished by rapid infiltrative growth, early metastasis, and a high risk of disability, which determines the significant medical and social importance of these pathologies [3]. According to international data, primary bone tumors account for less than 5% of all malignant neoplasms in children; however, they are often diagnosed at advanced stages [2,4]. This is mainly due to the nonspecific nature of their clinical manifestations and insufficient oncological alertness at the level of primary healthcare. In developing countries, this issue is even more relevant because of limited access to specialized medical care and modern diagnostic technologies [5].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, bone tumors constitute approximately 1–2% of all newly diagnosed malignant neoplasms [6]. At the same time, the prevalence and clinical-radiological characteristics of these diseases among children and adolescents remain insufficiently studied. Clinically, bone tumors are often manifested by nonspecific symptoms such as pain, swelling, and limitation of movement, which may lead to misdiagnosis and delayed detection [7,8]. Radiological imaging plays a crucial role in the diagnosis of these diseases. Conventional radiography is considered the primary imaging modality for initial assessment, while computed tomography provides detailed evaluation of bone structure, and magnetic resonance imaging plays a leading role in assessing intramedullary extension and soft tissue involvement of the tumor [9,10]. Nevertheless, the differential diagnosis between malignant and benign bone tumors remains challenging [10,12]. Therefore, studying the clinical and radiological characteristics of bone tumors in children and adolescents under the conditions of Uzbekistan is highly relevant.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the clinical and radiological characteristics of primary bone tumors in children and adolescents and to identify features associated with malignancy.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective study was conducted between 2022 and 2025 at the Republican Oncology Center, the Republican Center of Pediatric Hematology, Oncology and Clinical Immunology, and the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology. The study included 41 patients aged 5 to 60 years with primary bone

tumors who underwent diagnostic evaluation and treatment during the study period. Both malignant and benign primary bone tumors were included in the analysis.

Inclusion criteria:

- presence of a primary bone tumor;
- availability of radiological examinations (conventional radiography, computed tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging);
- histopathological confirmation of the diagnosis.

Exclusion criteria:

- secondary (metastatic) bone lesions;
- absence of histopathological confirmation;
- incomplete clinical or radiological data.

Radiological Examination Methods

All patients underwent standard conventional radiography of the affected anatomical region at the initial diagnostic stage. Computed tomography (CT) was performed in cases requiring detailed evaluation of the pattern of bone destruction, cortical involvement, and the presence of mineralized tumor components. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was performed according to standard protocols and included T1- and T2-weighted sequences. In some patients, diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) and contrast-enhanced MRI examinations were also performed.

- MRI analysis included assessment of the following parameters:
- tumor signal intensity on T1- and T2-weighted images;
- presence of diffusion restriction;
- pattern of contrast enhancement (homogeneous or heterogeneous);
- presence of bone marrow edema and bone marrow infiltration;
- presence and extent of the soft tissue component.

Analysis of Clinical and Imaging Data

The following parameters were analyzed:

patient age and sex;

tumor localization and affected side;

duration of symptoms and clinical complaints;

maximum tumor size;

pattern of tumor growth (endophytic, exophytic, or mixed);

tumor margins (smooth or irregular);

type of bone destruction (focal, diffuse, lytic, or osteoplastic);

presence and type of periosteal reaction;

presence of a soft tissue component;

degree of vascularization assessed by color Doppler ultrasonography using a 0–3-point scale.

Histopathological Confirmation

Histopathological confirmation was performed in all patients. The diagnosis was established based on fine-needle aspiration biopsy, core (trephine) biopsy, or histological examination of surgical specimens obtained after tumor resection. Tumor types were classified according to established histopathological classification criteria.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis included descriptive and comparative methods. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean values and standard deviations, whereas categorical variables were presented as absolute numbers and percentages.

The Mann–Whitney U test was used for comparison of continuous variables, while the chi-square test or Fisher’s exact test was applied for categorical variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 41 pediatric and adolescent patients aged between 5 and 60 years were included in the study. The mean age was 25.7 ± 3.7 years (mean \pm standard deviation). Male predominance was observed, with 24 cases (58.5%), while female patients accounted for 17 cases (41.5%). The majority of patients (n = 32; 78.0%) were older than 10 years. In all cases, primary bone tumors were diagnosed and histopathologically confirmed.

Tumor Localization

The most common localization was the long tubular bones of the lower extremities, identified in 22 patients (53.7%). Among them, the femur was the most frequently affected bone (15 cases; 36.6%), followed by the tibia (6 cases; 14.6%) and the fibula (1 case; 2.4%). Involvement of the pelvic bones (ilium and sacrum) was detected in 6 patients (14.6%). Less common localizations included the humerus in 3 cases (7.3%), bones of the foot in 4 cases (9.8%), as well as the scapula, clavicle, vertebral column, and ribs, each observed in 1 patient (2.4%). Tumor involvement was predominantly unilateral, with no significant predominance of either the right or left side.

Clinical Manifestations

Pain in the affected bone region was observed in all patients (41 cases; 100%). Local swelling was recorded in 39 patients (95.1%). Limitation of joint movement was identified in 23 patients (56.1%), while gait disturbance or functional impairment of the affected limb was observed in 19 patients (46.3%). In some cases, the disease was also accompanied by systemic symptoms such as low-grade fever. A considerable proportion of patients experienced prolonged duration of symptoms before the diagnosis was established.

Histological Distribution of tumors.

Figure 1. Overall and Histological Distribution of Tumors into Benign and Malignant Groups

Tumor Size and Growth Pattern

Tumor size varied widely across the study population. In the benign tumor group, the mean size was 57.9 ± 42.6 mm (n = 12). In contrast, malignant tumors were significantly larger, with a mean size of 98.0 ± 46.2 mm (n = 29; p < 0.05). Thus, malignant tumors were characterized by considerably larger dimensions compared to benign lesions. Regarding the growth pattern, malignant tumors more frequently demonstrated mixed or endophytic growth, whereas exophytic growth was more commonly associated with benign tumors.

Comparative Analysis of Clinical and Radiological Features

For comparative analysis, patients were divided into two groups:

malignant bone tumors (n = 29);

benign bone tumors (n = 12).

Tumor Margins

Irregular tumor margins were observed in 100% of malignant tumors and in 58.3% of benign tumors. The difference between the groups was statistically significant (p < 0.001; Fisher’s exact test).

Type of Bone Destruction

Lytic and diffuse patterns of bone destruction were significantly more frequent in malignant tumors, whereas focal and osteoplastic patterns predominated in benign lesions ($p < 0.01$).

Periosteal Reaction

Periosteal reaction was detected in the majority of malignant tumors and was considerably less frequent in benign tumors. Aggressive periosteal reactions (spiculated, lamellated “onion-skin” type, and sunburst-like patterns) were observed exclusively in malignant tumors ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 1A. 19-year-old female patient with Ewing sarcoma

Plain radiography demonstrates rapidly progressive and aggressive cortical bone destruction of the humerus, which is a characteristic feature of Ewing sarcoma.

Soft Tissue Component

A soft tissue component was identified in 26 of 29 malignant tumor cases (89.7%), whereas it was present in only 3 of 12 benign tumor cases (25.0%). This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) Findings

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was used to evaluate the extent of tumor spread, bone marrow involvement, presence of a soft tissue component, and imaging features associated with aggressive tumor behavior.

On MRI, malignant bone tumors most commonly demonstrated hypointense signal on T1-weighted images and hyperintense signal on T2-weighted images, reflecting replacement of normal fatty bone marrow by tumor tissue. These signal characteristics were observed in the majority of malignant lesions and were significantly less frequent in benign tumors.

Figure 1B. 19-year-old female patient with Ewing sarcoma

B–C, sagittal T1-weighted (TR/TE 360/14) and STIR (TR/TE 3825/30) MR images demonstrate cortical bone thickening (arrow). In both sequences, a wide transition zone is present, along with mild edema in the adjacent deep soft tissues.

On diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI), diffusion restriction was predominantly observed in malignant tumors and was not seen in benign lesions. This finding is explained by increased cellularity and restricted water diffusion in malignant tissue.

After contrast administration, malignant tumors showed predominantly heterogeneous enhancement, reflecting the presence of viable tumor tissue, areas of necrosis, and variable degrees of vascularization. In some cases, contrast-enhanced MRI was used as a guide for biopsy to select the most viable tumor area while avoiding necrotic regions.

Bone marrow edema and bone marrow infiltration were significantly more common in malignant tumors compared to benign lesions. Although these findings are considered indicators of aggressive behavior, they do not always directly correlate with tumor malignancy grade and should be interpreted in combination with other clinical and imaging features.

The presence of a soft tissue component on MRI is one of the most important indicators of aggressive tumor behavior in children. In this study, this feature was observed in the majority of malignant tumors and was rarely seen in benign lesions, demonstrating its high diagnostic value.

Overall, the results of this study confirm that MRI is the primary imaging modality in the evaluation of bone tumors in children and adolescents. It provides detailed information on tumor extent, bone marrow involvement, soft tissue extension, and imaging features associated with aggressive behavior. Integrating MRI findings with radiographic and clinical data significantly improves preoperative diagnostic accuracy and contributes to the development of an optimal treatment strategy.

Discussion

Although the clinical and radiological features of malignant bone tumors are well described in the literature, their diagnostic value varies considerably depending on patient age, population characteristics, and regional factors. Most previous studies have been conducted in adult or mixed populations, while systematic investigations focused specifically on children and adolescents remain limited, particularly in Central Asian countries.

In the present study, a comprehensive analysis of the clinical and radiological characteristics of primary bone tumors was performed based on data from the Republican Oncology Center, the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology, and the Center for Pediatric Hematology, Oncology and Clinical Immunology in Uzbekistan. In all cases, the diagnosis was mandatorily confirmed by histopathological examination. The results demonstrated that, in pediatric patients, malignant bone tumors are significantly associated with larger tumor size, irregular margins, lytic or diffuse bone destruction, aggressive periosteal reaction, and the presence of a soft tissue component. These features reliably differentiate malignant bone tumors from benign lesions.

It should be emphasized that the clinical significance of this study does not lie in the identification of novel radiological markers, but rather in the validation and quantitative assessment of well-established radiographic criteria in real clinical practice within the settings of specialized oncology centers in Uzbekistan. In resource-limited environments, where access to advanced diagnostic technologies may be uneven, the integrated interpretation of fundamental radiological features remains a key tool for the early detection of malignant bone tumors in children and adolescents.

An important aspect of this study is that a significant proportion of patients were referred to specialized care at advanced stages of the disease, indicating that delayed diagnosis at the primary healthcare level remains a persistent problem. In this context, strengthening the diagnostic value of imaging features such as periosteal reaction and the presence of a soft tissue

component may improve clinical vigilance and facilitate earlier referral of patients to specialized centers.

Overall, the findings of this study complement the existing literature and confirm the applicability of established clinical and radiological criteria of malignancy in pediatric populations in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This work helps to address the lack of regional data and may serve as a foundation for future studies aimed at improving diagnostic algorithms for bone tumors in children and adolescents.

Limitations

This study has several limitations, including its retrospective design and the relatively small number of patients. Nevertheless, the obtained data reflect real-world clinical practice at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology and the Center for Pediatric Hematology, Oncology and Clinical Immunology, providing clinically relevant information for the diagnostic evaluation of bone tumors in children and adolescents.

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